

Wedding songs (Biya-Nam) of Assamese Society: An analytical study

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Art is that form of creation which gives people joy, pleasure through the sense of beauty. Art is the perceived realization of God, human or objects, whether gross or subtle. Song is that form of art which emerges out of the cultural consciousness of human society.

Folk songs are the traditional songs in our Assamese society. Though initially these types of songs were in oral tradition, but in present time these are available in written form also. Wedding songs are one of the most notable traditional songs especially in Assamese society and it is one of the popular divisions of art too. Everywhere, from North to South, East to West wedding songs in their own languages are very popular among all the tribes or communities in Assam. Even at present time also, these songs and its discussion is very relevant as it represent the cultural heritage of our society.

This paper is an attempt to highlight about the various types of wedding songs, influence of modernization and technology on it and the mythological elements associated with it. The method used for this paper is descriptive and analytical. Data have been collected from direct observation of several marriage ceremonies and from a few relevant articles on it.

Keywords: Art, Marriage, Wedding songs, Mythological elements, Modernization